

**FACTORS INFLUENCING PREVALENCE OF TUBERCULOSIS
AMONG ADULT PATIENTS RECEIVING HEALTH SERVICES AT
CHINA UGANDA FRIENDSHIP HOSPITAL, NAGURU IN KAMPALA**

BY

RUBANGAKENE FRED

NOVEMBER 2024

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RUBANGAKENE FRED

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**A RESEARCH REPORT SUBMITTED TO UGANDA ALLIED HEALTH
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OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE AWARD OF
A DIPLOMA IN MEDICAL LABORATORY
TECHNOLOGY**

NOVEMBER 2024

DECLARATION

I **RUBANGAKENE FRED** here in declare that all the work in this research proposal is original and it has never been submitted to any institute for any academic award.

Signature Date

RUBANGAKENE FRED

(Student)

APPROVAL

This is to certify that this research proposal has been prepared by RUBANGAKENE FRED under my technical guidance and careful supervision and is ready for submission with my approval.

Signature

Date

Mr. EJALU DAVID LIVINGSTONE

(Supervisor)

DEDICATION

I dedicate this research work to my lovely parents for their diligent support during this entire research process, my brothers who encouraged me daily and supports me tirelessly I love you all dearly and to my supervisor for his guidance

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I thank Jehovah God for helping me complete this research successfully, am also grateful to the China Uganda Friendship Hospital to letting me carry out this study at their facility and I am grateful to all the participants of this study for their time and support, to my dearest friends Mao, Osiba, Agona, Moses thank you for not denying me your suggestions.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CDC:	Center for Disease Control
CUFH:	China Uganda Friendship Hospital
EMB:	Ethambutol
EPTB:	Extra-Pulmonary Tuberculosis
HIV:	Human Immune Virus
INH:	Isoniazid
MDR:	Multi Drug Resistance
NTLP:	National TB and leprosy Program
PZA:	Pyrazinamide
TB:	Tuberculosis
WHO:	World Health Organisation

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OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

- Prevalence:** A statistical concept referring to the number of cases of a disease that is present in a particular population in a given period of time.
- Factors:** Refers to aspect of behavior or lifestyle, environmental exposure or an inherited characteristic associated with increased likelihood of a disease.
- Incidence:** A measure of the probability of occurrence of a disease within a specific period of time.
- Immunity:** The state of being insusceptible or resistant to a noxious agent, process especially a pathogen or infectious disease.
- Mycobacterium:** A bacterium of group which includes the causative agents of tuberculosis.

ABSTRACT

Background: Tuberculosis is among the world's top infectious killer diseases and leading cause of death of people with HIV and also a major contributor to antimicrobial resistance. In Kampala, tuberculosis (TB) remains a major public health risk that raises death rates and expenses in terms of treatment.

Study Purpose: To assess the factors influencing the prevalence of Tuberculosis among adult patients accessing health services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital in Kampala by determining the prevalence of TB socio-economic factors influencing its prevalence and knowledge and awareness of adult patients on TB.

Study Methods: A quantitative cross-sectional study design was employed for this study using quantitative data analysis methods. The study population was 258 participants obtained using Kishi Leslie and data was collected from participants who consented to be part of the study using structured questionnaire.

Results: The findings showed that there was 4% prevalence of tuberculosis. For instance, among different education levels, individuals with no education (3.4%) and primary education (2.9%) had very low tuberculosis positivity rates, while secondary education (5.4%) and tertiary education (2.9%) also showed low positivity, income level analysis shows that individuals with low income (3.8%) and moderate income (4.1%) had slightly higher positivity rates compared to high-income individuals and Individuals aware of TB show a significantly lower positivity rate (3.3%) compared to those unaware (15.4%).

Conclusion: The prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients accessing health care services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru was 4%. In this study, the low-education level and low-income status influence the prevalence of tuberculosis and adequate knowledge about tuberculosis was identified among the study participants.

Recommendations: The study found low tuberculosis prevalence of (4%) but because of need to eliminate TB in Uganda, increased testing, treatment, and large-scale educational campaigns are necessary. The study highlighted that low education and income levels were significant factors in TB prevalence. It also noted that awareness and knowledge about TB were mostly spread through radios, televisions, and health facilities. Therefore, ongoing public education and patient awareness programs are essential to combat TB effectively.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This research is about the factors influencing prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital (CUFH), Naguru.

This chapter consists of the following; background of the study, problem statement, general objectives, specific objectives, research questions, significance of the study, and scope of the study.

1.1 Background

Tuberculosis refers to an infectious airborne disease caused mainly by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and majorly affects the lungs leading to pulmonary tuberculosis and other sites in the body which is termed as extra pulmonary tuberculosis (Adane *et al.*, 2020). Globally, tuberculosis is still a big disease burden where it is estimated that two billion people of the world's population get infected with tuberculosis (TB), with 10.6 million becoming ill each year and over 3,500 people lose their lives to TB each day totaling 1.3 million deaths each year (CDCGlobal, 2024). This makes tuberculosis among the world's top infectious killer diseases.

Tuberculosis is an airborne-transmitted disease transmitted through inhalation of droplets from contagious individuals by coughing, speaking, singing and sneezing (Migliori *et al.*, 2021). The prominent clinical manifestation of tuberculosis include cough, weight loss, fever, night sweats, bloody sputum, chest pain and fatigue (Sahra *et al.*, 2024).

Tuberculosis is diagnosed by various methods but the most recommended method by World Health Organization is by use of biomolecular tests as the initial diagnostic test in a suspect patient involving the use of Xpert MTB/RIF Ultra assays. Other diagnostic methods involves direct microscopy by use of Ziehl–Nielsen (ZN) staining though culture of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in a suitable medium remains the gold standard diagnostic test (Gill *et al.*, 2022). The treatment of Drug sensitive tuberculosis involves use of combination of four antibiotics: isoniazid (INH), rifampicin (RIF), pyrazinamide (PZA) and ethambutol (EMB) which are administered under observed treatment to prevent resistance (Alsayed & Gunosewoyo, 2023).

Globally, it is estimated that two billion people which is about one fourth of the world's total population may be infected with tuberculosis (TB), with 10.6 million becoming ill each year

and over 1.3 million deaths each year (CDCGlobal, 2024). Of the infected individuals, around 30 percent of the cases are missed by healthcare screenings and diagnostics and do not get the care they need, leading to poor health outcomes and an increased spread of TB in communities (CDCGlobal, 2024).

In Africa, the burden accounts for 25% of the total global burden due to several risk factors with HIV infection has a major driver (Mbuya *et al.*, 2023). In Africa, 2.5 million people fell ill with TB in 2022 with estimated 424,000 people dying from the disease. Nigeria and Democratic Republic of Congo have the highest prevalence of tuberculosis according to the World Health Organization Tuberculosis Report 2023.

In East Africa, the pooled prevalence of tuberculosis could not be obtained but East African countries such Ethiopia, Rwanda, Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda are listed among the 39 high burden countries with tuberculosis (WHO, 2021). Among, those countries, Ethiopia is one of the highest burden countries with regards to TB, TB/ HIV, and MDR-TB.

Uganda, according to the World Health Organization Tuberculosis Report 2023 is among the world's thirty high-burden countries for TB and TB/HIV co-infection with approximately 91,000 Ugandans getting sick of TB with 32% of them being HIV-infected each year. There is also an overall increasing trend of tuberculosis from 2013 to 2022 The proportions of new and previously-treated TB cases caused by multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) and rifampin-resistant TB were estimated at 1% and 12%, respectively in 2018 (Aceng *et al.*, 2024).

Kampala has been noted as the area with the highest prevalence of TB in the country with One in four TB cases notified in Uganda are from Kampala (Kirenga *et al.*, 2015). In a recent study done at Mulago National Referral Hospital in Kampala, Uganda, the prevalence of tuberculosis was 8.5% and it was more frequent among HIV patients due to lowered immunity. Hence, the need for early detection of TB before dissemination particularly among people who use alcohol and people with HIV (Kyagulanyi *et al.*, 2022). Thus, this study aims at exploring the various factors influencing the prevalence of Tuberculosis so that these findings can be used to implement Ministry of Health programs so that the prevalence of TB is decreased.

1.2 Problem statement

In Kampala, tuberculosis (TB) remains a major public health risk that raises death rates and expenses in terms of treatment especially for those who are infected with HIV and also those

not infected with HIV coupled with the rise in TB Antimicrobial resistance. This can be accounted to the fact that Kampala is an urban area and its overcrowded.

In a community-based study done by Robsky *et al.*(2020) showed that the prevalence of tuberculosis among adults in Kampala was 62% and this was accounted to the geographical distribution of disease in Kampala which is a urban area and the fact that interventions targeted at small geographical scales have not been widely implemented for TB.

Tuberculosis leads to reduced labor force since ill individuals cannot take part in work, exhausts government health budgets, depresses household savings, and disrupts local economies and finally it leads to death (Silva *et al.*, 2021).

The Ministry of Health of Uganda have adapted the World Health Organization's (WHO) End TB Strategy of reducing TB deaths by 90% and incidence by 80% by 2035 through establishment of National TB and leprosy Program (NTLP) for easy monitoring of tuberculosis (Buregyeya *et al.*, 2022).

Despite the various interventions by the government of Uganda, the prevalence of tuberculosis in Uganda still remains high due to various factors which are either socio-economic and awareness and knowledge about TB and hence this research will aim at finding out the factors.

1.3.0 Main Objective

1. To determine the factors that influence the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital.

1.3.1 Specific Objectives

1. To determine the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital.
2. To determine the socio-economic factors influencing the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital.
3. To determine the level of awareness and knowledge of the adult patients on Tuberculosis at China Uganda Friendship Hospital.

1.3.2 Research questions

1. What is the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital?

2. What are the socio-economic factors influencing the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital?
3. What is the level of awareness and knowledge of the adult patients on Tuberculosis at China Uganda Friendship Hospital?

1.4 Significance of the study

The results of this study shall be important in designing measures and implementing for the prevention and control of Tuberculosis.

The results of the study will be used to determine the working control measures and generate vital interventions to be put in place in order to reduce the incidence of TB and improve its management at the hospital facility.

The results of this study will also enable proper planning and allocation of resources to the facility by the ministry of health and supporting implementing partners to aid and facilitate tuberculosis screening which will improve on early detection as well as prevention of TB.

This study will also provide women countrywide with adequate information about cervical cancer and the need for regular screening thereby increasing on their level of awareness.

The research shall help me succeed in achieving an award of a Diploma in Medical Laboratory Technology as a pre-requisite in the partial fulfilment for qualification of the profession.

1.5.0 Scope of the study

1.5.1 Content scope

The research study was intended to assess the factors that influence the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital satisfaction but specifically; evaluating the social-economic factors and awareness and knowledge on TB influencing the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients and finally determine the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients.

1.5.2 Geographical scope

This study was conducted at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru located in Nakawa division in Kampala, central region of Uganda.

1.5.3 Time scope

The study was conducted for about two months from June to July 2024

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter reviews the works of the previous researchers related to the topic of study and it will be discussed under the following sub-heading; the prevalence of Tuberculosis at China Uganda Friendship Hospital Naguru, socio-economic factors influencing the prevalence of Tuberculosis and awareness and knowledge on Tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital Naguru.

The literature review was got from, text books, articles, web pages, authorities, bulletins, magazines, newspapers, journals, other research findings and the internet.

2.1 Prevalence of Tuberculosis

In a systematic review and meta-analysis study done by Cohen *et al.*(2019) to determine global prevalence of latent tuberculosis using 88 studies from 36 countries published between 2005 and 2018 from the databases MEDLINE, Embase, Scopus and Web of Science for the articles. The findings of the study showed that the global prevalence of tuberculosis was 24.8% which correlated well with the World Health Organization.

In a systematic review and meta-analysis study done by Sathiyamoorthy *et al.*(2020) to determine the prevalence of pulmonary tuberculosis in India using 13 articles with 16 individual studies from databases of Medline, Embase, Scopus, the Cochrane Library, Web of Science, and Google Scholar published between January 1, 1997, and December 31, 2018. The findings of the study showed that estimated to be 24.5% which was higher among males than females and in rural areas compared to urban areas.

However, another cross-sectional study done to determine prevalence and factors associated with tuberculosis infection in India in 443 clusters across during the period 2019 to 2021 by Selvaraju *et al.*(2023). Data was collected using interview method using a semi-structured interview schedule and sputum collection done on suspected individuals. The findings of the study showed that prevalence of TB infection was 22.6%.

In a systematic review and meta-analysis study done by Hailu *et al.*(2024) to determine prevalence of extra-pulmonary tuberculosis(EPTB) in Africa using five databases of which 105 studies published between 1990 and 2023 were included. The findings of the study showed that the pooled prevalence of EPTB among TB patients was 26% with the Eastern region having the highest prevalence of 32% and lowest in Western Africa.

In a systematic review and meta-analysis study done by Sisay Asgedom *et al.*(2023) to determine the pooled prevalence of tuberculosis among prisoners in sub-Saharan Africa using electronic biomedical databases such as Google Scholar, Web of Science, PubMed/Medline, EMBASE, and Science Direct where 40 articles published between 1997 and 2020 were used. The findings of the study showed that prevalence of TB infection among prisoners in Africa was 4.02%.

In a cross sectional study done by Mbuya *et al.*(2023) to determine the current prevalence of TB among the mining communities in Mererani, situated in Simanjiro District, northern Tanzania and assess factors associated with TB from April 2019 to November 2021. A total of 660 study participants, 330 mine workers and 330 from the general community were used for the study who were randomly selected. The findings of the study showed that prevalence of TB was 7% where participants from the general community had higher prevalence of TB 7.9% than the miners.

In a retrospective study done by Kyagulanyi *et al.*(2022) to determine the prevalence of concurrent pulmonary and extrapulmonary tuberculosis in Uganda in at Mulago National Referral Hospital in Kampala between January 2015 and December 2019. The findings of the study showed that the prevalence of concurrent PTB and EPTB was 8.5%.

2.2.0 Socio-economic factors influencing prevalence of Tuberculosis

2.2.1 Level of Education

In a convergent parallel mixed study done by Nidoi *et al.*(2021) to determine the impact of socio-economic factors on Tuberculosis treatment outcomes in north-eastern Uganda between April 2018 and March 2019. Data was collected in 10 TB Diagnostic & Treatment Units in the five southern districts of Moroto, Napak, Amudat, Nabilatuk and Nakapiripirit. Electronic data from the District Health Information System. The findings of the study showed that educated individuals had lower chances of getting infected with tuberculosis compared with uneducated individuals.

In a study done by Imam *et al.*(2021) to assess the possible impact of socioeconomic, income, and educational status on adverse effects of drug and their therapeutic episodes in patients targeted with a combination of tuberculosis interventions in New Delhi, India of which 1,011 patients were screened. The findings of the study showed that an increased incidence of

tuberculosis was found in patients who have finished high school compared to those who did not finish high school.

In a spatial autocorrelation analysis done by Wang *et al.*(2019) to explore the spatial distribution and socioeconomic influencing factors of TB in mainland China from 2013 to 2016 in 34 provincial-level administrative regions. Data and basic demographic information, including gender, age and occupation from 2013 to 2016 were obtained from the Public Health Science Data Center of the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention. The findings of the study showed that education level was directly associated with the incidence of Tuberculosis where the illiterate individuals had a higher incidence rate.

In a review study done by Duarte *et al.*(2018) to assess the effects of socio-economic determinants and co-morbidities (including HIV) on TB infection and disease. Data was collected from databases of PubMed and Scopus for studies written in English, French, Spanish or Portuguese that evaluated the socioeconomic determinants on TB. The findings of the study showed that lack of education increased the risk of being infected with tuberculosis while educated individuals were at a lower risk of getting the disease.

2.2.2 Income status

In a study done by Kirenga *et al.*(2015) to determine the tuberculosis risk factors among tuberculosis patients in Kampala, Uganda. Data was collected from 365 adult TB patients and used descriptive statistics to summarize their socio-demographic, clinical, radiological, sputum mycobacteriology and TB risk factors. The results of the study showed that poverty relating to low-income status was associated with the increased incidence of Tuberculosis among the poor individuals.

In a study done by Imam *et al.*(2021) to assess the possible impact of socioeconomic, income, and educational status on adverse effects of drug and their therapeutic episodes in patients targeted with a combination of tuberculosis interventions in New Delhi, India of which 1,011 patients were screened. The findings of the study showed that increased incidence of Tuberculosis was among poor individuals compared to the rich individuals.

In a community based cross sectional study done by Adane *et al.*(2020) to assess the prevalence and associated factors of Tuberculosis among Adult Household Contacts of Smear Positive Pulmonary Tuberculosis Patients Treated in Public Health Facilities of Haramaya District, Oromia Region, Eastern Ethiopia. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire through

face-to-face interview. The results of the study showed that the incidence of tuberculosis increased as the level of income decreased.

In a review study done by Duarte *et al.*(2018) to assess the effects of socio-economic determinants and co-morbidities (including HIV) on TB infection and disease. Data was collected from databases of PubMed and Scopus for studies written in English, French, Spanish or Portuguese that evaluated the socioeconomic determinants on TB. The findings of the study showed that low-income status and unemployment led to increased risk of an individual getting TB as compared to increased income status and employed individuals.

2.3.0 Awareness and knowledge of the adult patients on Tuberculosis

In a population based cross-sectional study done by Chen *et al.*(2019) in China in Zhejiang Province from October 2018 to December 2018 to evaluate the level of awareness of TB knowledge among residents. Data was collected door to door using unified standard electronic questionnaires, which measured four aspects: respondents' socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge, beliefs, and practices towards key information on TB, access to TB knowledge, and understanding of TB treatment behaviors and policies from 7174 individuals who were randomly selected to participate in this survey. The results of the study showed that rate of awareness of key information on TB was found to be 48.0% while exhibiting a good understanding of the transmission route at 80.8%, curable outcome at 78.3%, and designated treatment sites at 67.0% of TB and the final conclusion was that residents in Zhejiang Province generally lacked key information about TB, which is not conducive to the early detection and treatment of TB.

In an exploratory study conducted between January and December 2016 by Sharma *et al.*,(2020) to explore the awareness and perceptions of TB patients in a tertiary care center in northern India. Data was collected using structured and validated interview schedule was used to assess participants knowledge and perception regarding TB comprising of 41 questions from 1,000 study participants. The results of the study showed that 61.85% of the study participants had highest knowledge score about tuberculosis sign and symptoms and 52.7% in the aspect of prevention and treatment and however a lower proportion knew about the its cause and around half of the subjects disagreed that TB is a major health problem.

In a cross-sectional study done by Dorji *et al.*(2020) to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice on TB among the teacher trainees of Samtse College of Education in Bhutan from

September 1st to September 30th, 2019. Data was collected using a standardized pretested questionnaire from 420 trainees. The results of the study showed that majority of the trainees had poor knowledge on TB, especially among the trainees in senior years of college and those who had never suffered from TB and attitude towards TB was good especially among the female trainees. However, the overall practice and prevention was poor among the participants.

In a cross-sectional study done by Junaid *et al.* (2021) to assess TB stigma in light of knowledge, attitudes, and preventive practices among individuals in Lagos, Nigeria. Data was collected by using a pretested, semi-structured, interviewer administered questionnaire from 317 participants. The findings of the study showed that 91.8% of the participants were aware of TB, only 2.4% of the participants had good knowledge about TB, more than half had positive attitudes towards TB and about a third had good preventative practices. Hence, most participants were aware of TB although knowledge, attitude and practice levels were very poor.

In a quasi-experimental study done to evaluate the effect of an educational intervention on awareness among patients with pulmonary TB attending the chest clinic in Omdurman Military Medical Corps Hospital in Sudan for follow-up during the period April–July 2018 by Yousif *et al.* (2021). Data was collected using structured questionnaire from 190 patients. The findings of the study showed that participants' knowledge about aspects of TB was generally poor which included the nature of the causative organism, modes of transmission and measures needed for the control and prevention.

In a cross-sectional study done in seven regions and two city administrations of Ethiopia to better understand TB-related knowledge, attitudes, and practices and generate evidence for policy and decision-making by Datiko *et al.* (2019). Data was collected from 3,503 participants who were randomly selected and interviewed. The findings of the study showed that the majority (95.5%) had heard about TB, but only 25.8% knew that TB is caused by bacteria. Cough was reported as the commonest means of TB transmission and majority (85.3%) knew that TB could be cured.

In a community based cross-sectional study done by Kayiza (2019) to assess knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards TB transmission among migrant Somali population living in Kisenyi slum, Kampala, Uganda between June and July 2017. Data was collected from 410 respondents using a questionnaire. The findings of the study showed that only 42% had

adequate knowledge about TB and inadequate knowledge was apparent in questions relating to TB signs and prevention.

2.4.0 Summary

The prevalence of Tuberculosis as shown by the previous studies has increased and this has been linked to numerous factors such as socio-economic factors for example income status and level of education and awareness and knowledge on TB among the various stakeholders. This calls for the need for the massive education and awareness of the communities about the transmission and control of Tuberculosis.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter describes the study design, study area, study population, sample size, sampling technique, sampling procedure, data collection method, data collection tools, data collection procedure, study variables, quality control, data analysis and presentation, ethical considerations, study limitations and dissemination of results.

3.1 Study Design

A cross-sectional study design was used for this study. The design utilized quantitative methods to obtain measurable data from the participants and it allowed the researcher to carry out the study in shortest period of time, study both the independent and the dependent variable at the same time and it is cost effective.

3.2 Study Area

The study was carried out in China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru in Kampala, Central Uganda found in the coordinates of latitude 0.32895° or 0° 19' 44" north and longitude 32.60673° or 32° 36' 24" east. It is meant to decongest Mulago National Referral Hospital; the hospital is primarily intended to serve residents of Nakawa Division, Kampala metropolitan area and other needful Ugandans. The hospital has a bed capacity of 100 beds; it has four operating rooms, a maternity ward, a pediatric unit, teenage center (adolescent health unit), a blood bank, radiology department (including a CT scanner) and housing for medical staff. The study area serves a large population and has a combination of people with various socioeconomic statuses, level of education, living conditions, densely populated, and various water sources for routine home use.

3.3 Study Population

The study was conducted among adult patients visiting the laboratory for tuberculosis diagnostic services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital-Naguru.

3.4 Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using standard formula by Kishi Leslie (1965). Sample size determination formula is below:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 PQ}{d^2}$$

Where:

n- required sample size

P- the proportion of attribute in the population (obtained from prevalence)

Q- product of P(1-P)

d- permissible error set at 0.05 or (5%)

Z- standard deviation set at 1.96 at a confidence interval of 95%

Using as 21.3% as prevalence of Tuberculosis in Uganda, (Aceng *et al.*, 2024)

$$n = \frac{Z^2 PQ}{d^2} \qquad n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times (0.213) \times (1-0.213)}{(0.05)^2} \qquad n = 258$$

Therefore, the sample size for this study was 258 participants. From this sample size data on the prevalence, socio-economic factors and awareness and knowledge on TB was obtained.

3.5 Sampling Technique

The simple random sampling technique was employed because this helped to reduce on bias that could be created by selective and purposive recruitment of participants and provides equal opportunity to all the participants of the study to be recruited for the study.

3.6 Sampling Procedure

The participants were asked to randomly pick a piece of paper from the 400 pieces of paper with either YES or NO written on them. Those who chose YES will be included in the study and those who chose NO will be excluded.

3.7 Data Collection Method

The researcher used interview method to collect measurable data giving a clear picture of the problem and information that was reliable and reproducible. The interview method allowed the researcher to clearly explain the questions to the respondents that they didn't clearly understand with the help of a well-structured questionnaire to collect data on socio-economic factors and awareness and knowledge on TB. Prevalence data was collected by collecting sputum samples and running the test using GeneXpert machine because it is very sensitive and specific for detecting Mycobacterium causing TB.

3.8 Data Collection Tools

The researcher used interview method using a structured questionnaire to collect measurable data giving a clear picture of the problem and information that is reliable and reproducible. The interview method allowed the researcher to clearly explain the questions to the respondents that they didn't clearly understand with the help of a well-structured questionnaire to collect data on socio-economic factors and awareness and knowledge on TB. Prevalence data was collected using GeneXpert machine for running tests on sputum samples collected.

3.9 Data Collection Procedure

The data was collected by interviewing participants face to face using the questionnaire. The responses from the participants were recorded in the questionnaire by the researcher or by the respondent. For the participants who could not read English the researcher and the research assistants were verbally interpreted into the respondents' local language. Data for prevalence was collected by giving respondents sputum mugs and instructing them to collect sputum in it and the sputum samples was later tested using a GeneXpert machine.

3.10.0 Quality Control

3.10.1 Selection Criteria

3.10.1.1 Inclusion Criteria

Patients who visited the laboratory for Tuberculosis diagnostic services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru were included in the study.

3.10.1.2 Exclusion Criteria

Patients who visited the laboratory not for Tuberculosis diagnostic services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru were excluded from the study.

3.10.2 Pretesting of the Research Tool

A preliminary study was carried out first before the actual data collection in order to identify potential problems in the data collection by visiting the study area and sampling 10 respondents to check questionnaire validity; the questionnaire was adjusted accordingly.

3.10.3 Training of Research Assistants

The researcher recruited and trained two research assistants to help carry out the study and used the data collection tools to capture the data from the respondents. and how to maintain confidentiality of respondent information.

3.10.4 Giving Ample Time for Data Collection

The study was carried out in a period of two months (June 2024- July, 2024) following the work plan.

3.10.5 Adherence to Standard Operating Procedure.

The researcher strictly adhered to the participant inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure that only the suitable respondents are recruited for the study.

3.11 Study Variables

This study only studied the independent variables and the dependent variable.

3.11.1 Dependent Variable

The dependent variable under the study was prevalence of Tuberculosis among adult patients.

3.11.2 Independent Variable

The independent variables under study included: socio-economic factors and awareness and knowledge about TB.

3.12 Data Analysis and Presentation

Data was clearly analyzed during the process of its collection and after collection to avoid unnecessary data. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS, Microsoft excel, scientific calculator and the processed data presented in tables and figures.

3.13 Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance letter was obtained from the Hospital Research committee that will give permission and approval to carry out the study. The researcher will maintain the anonymity of the participants by assigning them codes instead of using their names, consent is to be obtained from each participant after properly explaining the nature and purpose of the study to them, participation is voluntary and no money will be paid to any participant. The respondents are free to withdraw from the study if they chose at any time and the researcher will ensure that the information obtained from the participants is kept confidential.

3.14 Study Limitations

The study design employed in the study did not analyze cause-effect relations of variables and because of the small population size the data may not be completely representative of the entire study population and also the short time period of the study affected the results.

3.15 Dissemination of Results

After completion of data analysis and presentation, results, a conclusion was made and compiled together to make a research report which was disseminated to the Medical Director China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Uganda Allied Health Examinations Board, School of Medical Laboratory Technology-Jinja and Supervisor.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses the findings of the study on the factors influencing the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients visiting the laboratory for tuberculosis diagnostic services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital-Naguru in Kampala. All the results are presented in line with the specific study objectives. Using two hundred fifty-eight (258) participants, the prevalence, socio-economic factors and knowledge and awareness of tuberculosis was determined as presented here in this chapter.

4.1 Socio-demographic factors of study population

The study on TB prevalence included 258 participants and showed slightly higher positivity rates among males, who accounted for 133 individuals (52%) with a TB positivity rate of 4.5% (6 cases), compared to females, with 125 participants (42%) and a positivity rate of 3.2% (4 cases). In terms of age, the 21-35 age group was the largest, with 107 people (41.5%) and a 4.7% positivity rate (5 cases). The 36-40 age group had 104 individuals (40.3%) and a positivity rate of 3.8% (4 cases). The youngest age group (<20) had 24 participants (9.3%) with one positive case (4.2%), and no TB cases were found among those over 40 (23 individuals, 8.9%).

For religious affiliation, Christians represented 172 participants (66.7%) with a TB positivity rate of 2.9% (5 cases), while Muslims accounted for 86 participants (33.3%) with a slightly higher positivity rate of 4.0% (4 cases). Marital status showed that married individuals comprised the largest group, with 170 people (65.9%) and a 3.5% positivity rate (6 cases), while divorced participants (25 people, 9.7%) had the highest positivity rate at 8% (2 cases). Those who had never married included 63 individuals (24.4%) with a TB positivity rate of 3.2% (2 cases).

Table 1: showing socio-demographic factors

Study variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Status of tuberculosis	
				positive	negative
Gender	Male	133	52%	6 (4.5%)	127 (96.6%)
	females	125	42%	4 (3.2%)	125 (97.1%)
Age ranges	<20	24	9.3%	1(4.2%)	23(95.8%)
	21-35	107	41.5%	5 (4.7%)	139 (95.1%)
	36-40	104	40.3%	4 (3.8%)	100 (96.2%)
	>40	23	8.9%	0 (0.0%)	23(100%)
Religious affiliation	Christian	172	66.7%	1 (2.9%)	33 (97.1%)
	Muslim	86	33.3%	9 (4.0%)	215 (96.0%)
Marital status	Married	170	65.9%	6 (3.5%)	164 (96.5%)
	Divorced	25	9.7%	2(8%)	23(92%)
	Never married	63	24.4%	2(3.2%)	61(96.8%)

4.2 Prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital

The study showed that out of the 258 participants, majority of respondents 227 (96.1%) did not have tuberculosis infection (were negative) and minority of the participants had tuberculosis 10 (3.9%).

Table 2: showing Tuberculosis status of study participants

Status	Frequency	Percent (%)
positive	10	3.9
negative	248	96.1
Total	258	100.0

Figure 1: Status of tuberculosis of study participants

4.2.0 Socio-economic factors influencing prevalence of tuberculosis

The study showed that individuals with no education had the highest TB prevalence (5.4%), while those with secondary or higher education levels had lower prevalence rates. Income level also influenced TB prevalence, with the highest rates observed among low-income participants (4.1%), and the lowest among high-income participants (2.9%). Urban residents had a slightly higher TB prevalence (4.0%) compared to rural residents (2.9%).

Employment status played a significant role, as employed individuals exhibited a higher TB prevalence (4.6%) compared to unemployed or retired participants, who reported no cases. Among different occupations, cleaners had the highest TB prevalence (11.1%), followed by security personnel and business persons. Those in other occupations had a lower prevalence

rate. The working and living conditions at the workplace also impacted TB prevalence, with poorer conditions associated with higher rates (8.7%) compared to good conditions (1.9%).

Table 3: Showing socio-economic factors influencing prevalence of tuberculosis

Study variable	Category	Frequency	Percent age	Status of tuberculosis	
				positive	negative
Education level	None	93	36.0%	5 (5.4%)	88 (94.6%)
	Primary	29	11.2%	1 (3.4%)	28 (96.6%)
	secondary	102	39.5%	3 (2.9%)	99 (97.1%)
	Tertiary and above	34	13.2%	1 (2.9%)	33 (97.1%)
Level of income	low	145	56.2%	6 (4.1%)	139 (95.1%)
	moderate	79	30.6%	3(3.8%)	76(96.2%)
	high	34	13.2%	1(2.9%)	33(97.1%)
Residence of women	Rural	34	13.2%	1 (2.9%)	33 (97.1%)
	Urban	224	86.8%	9 (4.0%)	215 (96.0%)
Occupation status	Employed	219	84.9%	10 (4.6%)	209 (95.4%)
	Unemployed	37	14.3%	0(0.0%)	37(100%)
	Retired	2	0.8%	0(0.0%)	2(100%)
Occupation type	Security personnel	26	10.1%	1(3.8%)	25(96.2%)
	Business person	107	41.5%	4 (3.7%)	103 (96.3%)

	Cleaner	9	3.5%	1(11.1%)	8(88.9%)
	Others	116	45.0%	4 (3.4%)	112 (96.6%)
Working and living conditions at the work place	Good	52	20.2%	1(1.9%)	51(98.1%)
	Fair	137	53.1%	3 (2.2%)	134 (97.8%)
	Poor	69	26.7%	6(8.7%)	63(91.3%)

4.3 Level of awareness and knowledge about tuberculosis among the adult patients

Table 4: Showing level of awareness and knowledge about tuberculosis among adult patients

Study variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Status of tuberculosis	
				positive	negative
Ever heard of TB	Yes	245	95%	8(3.3%)	237(96.7%)
	No	13	5%	2(15.4%)	11(84.6%)
Source of TB information	Health facility	55	21.3%	3(5.5%)	52(94.5%)
	Newspapers	33	12.8%	3(9.1%)	30(90.9%)
	Radios and TVs	158	61.2%	3 (1.9%)	155 98.1%
	Friends	12	4.7%	1(8.3%)	11(91.7%)
TB is transmitted by coughing	Yes	237	91.9%	10 (4.2%)	227 (95.8%)
	No	21	8.1%	0(0.0%)	21(100%)
Is TB treatable	Yes	240	93%	10 (4.2%)	230 (95.8%)
	No	18	7.0%	0(0.0%)	18(100%)
Duration of TB treatment	A few days	69	26.7%	2(2.9%)	67(97.1%)
	Long	88	34.1%	2(2.3%)	86(97.7%)
	Vey long	101	39.1%	6(5.9%)	95(94.1%)
Is TB spread by	Cough droplets	194	75.4%	8 (4.8%)	186 (95.9%)

	Eating utensils	12	4.7%	0 (0.0%)	12 (100%)
	Sharing clothes	5	1.9%	0 (0.0%)	5 (100%)
	I don't know	47	18.2%	2(4.3%)	45(95.7%)
Signs of TB are cough, bloody sputum and night sweats	Yes	194	75.2%	7 (3.6%)	187 (96.4%)
	No	18	7.0%	0 (0.0%)	18 (100%)
	I don't know	46	17.6	3 (6.5%)	43 (93.5%)
Is smoking and drinking risk factors for TB	Yes	220	85.3%	9(4.1%)	211 (95.9%)
	No	38	14.7%	1(2.6%)	37(97.4%)
Ever tested for TB	Yes	112	43.4%	6(5.4%)	106 (94.6%)
	No	146	56.6%	4(2.7%)	142 (97.3%)
Aware TB is tested at CUFH	Yes	206	79.8%	8(3.9%)	198 (96.1%)
	No	52	20.2%	2(3.8%)	50(96.2%)

Table 7 examines the impact of tuberculosis (TB) awareness on its prevalence. Individuals aware of TB show a significantly lower positivity rate (3.3%) compared to those unaware (15.4%). Various sources of TB information, such as health facilities and media, play a crucial role in spreading awareness, with media, particularly radios and TVs, showing the lowest positivity rates.

Awareness of TB transmission and symptoms correlates with lower positivity rates. Those knowledgeable about TB being spread by cough droplets and symptoms like cough, bloody sputum, and night sweats have lower infection rates. Additionally, awareness that smoking and

drinking are risk factors for TB is prevalent, contributing to a lower positivity rate. Testing history indicates higher positivity among those previously tested for TB.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the discussions, conclusion and recommendations of the study findings presented as the objectives.

5.1 Discussion

5.1.1 Prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru

The study found that the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients accessing health services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru was at 4% which is lower than other previous studies, this could be due to increased knowledge and awareness among the public and implementation of testing and treatment. The findings of this study closely correlate with the results of the study done by Sisay Asgedom *et al.*(2023) to determine the pooled prevalence of tuberculosis among prisoners in sub-Saharan Africa and the findings of the study showed that prevalence of tuberculosis was 4.02% and this could be attributed to improved diagnosis and increased knowledge about tuberculosis.

Similarly, in another study done by Mbuya *et al.*(2023) to determine the current prevalence of TB among the mining communities in Tanzania, the findings of the study also showed that the prevalence of tuberculosis was low at averagely 7.45%.

Also a study done by Kyagulanyi *et al.*(2022) to determine the prevalence of concurrent pulmonary and extrapulmonary tuberculosis in Uganda showed that the prevalence of tuberculosis was low which directly correlates with this study.

Contradicting to this study results, a study done by Cohen *et al.*(2019) to determine global prevalence of latent tuberculosis and the findings of the study showed that the prevalence of tuberculosis was 24.8% which was higher than this study results and this could be due to difference in the population in that study.

Also in another contradicting study done by Sathiyamoorthy *et al.*(2020) to determine the prevalence of pulmonary tuberculosis in India and the results of the study does not correlate with this study since was very high at 24.5%.

Also, other studies done by Hailu *et al.*(2024) in Africa and Selvaraju *et al.*(2023) in India contradict to the study in that the prevalence of tuberculosis is very high as compared to our study and this could be due to difference in the study populations and study area.

5.1.2 Socio-economic factors influencing the prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital

5.1.2.1 Level of Education

The data was analysed and it revealed that level of education is directly associated with the prevalence of tuberculosis where the respondents who had not attained higher level of education(No formal education and primary education at 5.4% and 3.4% respectively) were the most affected group with tuberculosis and the least affected are those who attained higher level of education(secondary and tertiary both at 2.9% positive TB cases) and this could be due to poor living conditions and lack of knowledge among the participants who attended only high school or lower compared to those who attended tertiary institutions and above.

These findings corresponds to a study done by Nidoi *et al.*(2021) to assess the impact of socio-economic factors on Tuberculosis treatment outcomes in north-eastern Uganda and the findings of the study showed that the prevalence of tuberculosis was lower in educated individuals as compared to those who were uneducated and this could be due to the fact that lack of education or low education level has a significant impact on knowledge and awareness about tuberculosis.

Similarly studies by Wang *et al.*(2019) in mainland China and Duarte *et al.*(2018) where in both the findings showed that lack of education increased the risk of being infected with tuberculosis while educated individuals were at a lower risk of getting the disease and this directly correlates with this study.

However, in a contradicting study done by Imam *et al.*(2021) to assess the showed that that the possible impact of socioeconomic, income, and educational status on adverse effects of drug and their therapeutic episodes in patients targeted with a combination of tuberculosis interventions in New Delhi, India. The results of the study showed that increased incidence of tuberculosis was higher among those who finished high school and less among those who did not finish high school.

5.1.2.2 Income status

The results of the study showed that there was association between income status of the adult patients and prevalence of tuberculosis where there was increased positive cases among the low(4.1%) and moderate-income(3.8%) groups and decreased positive cases among the high-income group patients(2.9%) and this could be due to the fact that low and moderate-income group may be living poor conditions and overcrowded areas and also may have more exposure to the disease at their work places.

Similarly, in a study done by Kirenga *et al.*(2015) in Kampala, Uganda to determine the tuberculosis risk factors among tuberculosis patients showed that the highest prevalence of tuberculosis was among participants in the low income status and the least prevalence was among the high income status participants which directly correlates with the results of the study.

Similarly studies by Imam *et al.*(2021), Adane *et al.*(2020) and Duarte *et al.*(2018) where in all the studies, the findings showed the incidence of tuberculosis increased as the level of income decreased and this directly correlates with this study and this could be due to the fact that the higher the income status the better access to good care, proper treatment and feeding and also better living conditions.

5.1.3 Awareness and knowledge of the adult patients on Tuberculosis

The results of the study showed that majority of the respondents knew about the transmission(91.9%), TB treatability(93%), signs and symptoms(75.2%), prevention and some the risk factors of tuberculosis(85.3%) and this could be due to the various awareness programs done by the ministry to create awareness about and tuberculosis and also the health care facility through educating the patients and encouraging them to test for the disease.

Similarly, in a study done by Sharma *et al.*,(2020) to assess explore the awareness and perceptions of TB patients in a tertiary care center in northern India and the findings of the study showed that majority of the participants had high knowledge about tuberculosis in terms of signs and symptoms and moderate knowledge in terms of prevention and treatment and this correlates with the findings of the study.

Similar to this study results, a study done by Datiko *et al.*(2019) to better understand TB-related knowledge, attitudes, and practices and generate evidence for policy and decision-making in Ethiopia showed that majority of the respondents has enough knowledge on tuberculosis in terms of transmission and treatment.

Contradicting to this study results, in studies done by Chen *et al.*(2019) in China, Dorji *et al.*(2020) in Bhutan, Junaid *et al.*(2021) in Nigeria, Yousif *et al.*(2021) in Sudan and Kayiza(2019) in Uganda showed that the knowledge of the participants in terms awareness, signs, symptoms transmission and measures for the control and prevention of tuberculosis was poor and this could be due to poor health education, low levels of education and limited access to information and technology.

5.2 Conclusion

The prevalence of tuberculosis among adult patients accessing health care services at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru was 4%. In this study, the low-education level and low-income status directly influence the prevalence of tuberculosis and adequate knowledge about tuberculosis was identified among the study participants.

5.3 Recommendation

Therefore, the prevalence of tuberculosis in this study was 4% which was low but the Ministry of Health aim is to completely eliminate TB from Uganda hence continuous testing and treatment must be increased by Ministry of Health and CUFH to eliminate the cases and initiate similar studies to monitor trends of Tuberculosis and knowledge about it should also be implemented in large scale across the country.

In this study, low education level and income status were influencing factors for the prevalence of TB and hence regular sensitizing and education by Ministry of Health and China Uganda Friendship Hospital are necessary to create awareness.

In this study, there was adequate knowledge and awareness and knowledge on TB mostly through radios and Televisions and health facilities and hence the Ministry of Health and CUFH must continue the education of patients and the general public on TB.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: CONSENT FORM

My name is **RUBANGAKENE FRED**, a student of medical laboratory training school Jinja. I am conducting a study on factors influencing the prevalence of Tuberculosis with among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital. I humbly invite you to take part in this study by answering some of the questions found within the questionnaire.

The purpose of this study is to determine factors influencing the prevalence of Tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital.

Your participation in this study is voluntary. You can decline and to withdraw your consent from the study at any stage during the study without loss of benefits or any penalties. Your name will not be used on any of the data collection forms but you will be assigned a participant unique code. Your information will be kept confidential and will not be shared with anyone and answering this questionnaire will take only 15 minutes of your time.

You will not be paid to take part in the study but you get to find out about factors influencing the prevalence of Tuberculosis among patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital and the results of this study will also help the to enable prioritization and management of the disease. There are no risks identified to be associated with this study.

Participants' declaration

I have read or have been read to the above information and fully understand the purpose of this study and I therefore voluntarily agree and consent to participate in this study.

Signature/ thumbprint..... Date.....

APPENDIX II: QUESTIONNAIRE

QUESTIONNAIRE ON DETERMINATION OF FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PREVALENCE OF TUBERCULOSIS AMONG ADULT PATIENTS AT CHINA UGANDA FRIENDSHIP HOSPITAL, NAGURU.

I am **RUBANGAKENE FRED** a final year diploma student of Medical Laboratory training school Jinja. I am conducting a study on factors influencing the prevalence of Tuberculosis among adult patients at China Uganda Friendship Hospital.

Instructions

Tick in the boxes provided for appropriate answers

Fill in the blank spaces provided where necessary

Respondent Code.....

Date.....

Section A: Socio-demographic factors

1. What is your age?

- A. ≤ 20 years
- B. 21-35 years
- C. 36-40 years
- D. ≥ 40 years

2. What is your marital status?

- A. Married
- B. Divorced
- C. Never married

3. What is your religious affiliation?

- A. Christian
- B. Muslim

4. What is your tribe?

- A. Muganda
- B. Munyankole

- C. Itesot
- D. Luo
- E. Others

Section B: Socio-economic factors

5. What is your education level?

- A. None
- B. Primary
- C. Secondary
- D. Tertiary and above

6. What is your income status?

- A. Low
- B. Moderate
- C. High

7. What is your place of residence?

- A. Rural
- B. Urban

8. What is your employment status?

- A. Employed
- B. Unemployed
- C. Retired

9. What is your occupation?

- A. Security personnel
- B. Business person
- C. Cleaner

D. Others, specify.....

10. How is your living and working condition in relation to the spread of TB? (Tick Good if spread very much reduced, Poor if spread is very high and Fair if spread is somehow reduced)

a) Good

b) Poor

c) Fair

Section C: Awareness regarding Tuberculosis and uptake of Tuberculosis screening

10. Have you ever heard of Tuberculosis?

Yes

No

11. What was the main source of information?

A. Health facilities

D. Friends

B. Newspapers

C. Radios and TV

12. Can a person get TB from air when a person with TB coughs?

A. Yes

B. No

13. Do you think TB can be treated?

A. Yes

B. No

14. If yes, how long is the treatment?

A. A few days

B. Long

C. Very long

15. Do you think TB can be transmitted through? (Tick where appropriate)

A. Cough droplets

B. Eating utensils

C. Sharing clothes

D. I don't know

16. Do you think cough, bloody sputum and night sweats are signs of TB?

A. Yes

B. No

C. I don't know

17. Do you think smoking and excessive drinking alcohol are some of the risk factors for TB?

A. Yes B. No C. I don't know

18. Have you ever tested for TB?

A. Yes B. No

19. Are you aware that TB testing is done at China Uganda Friendship Hospital, Naguru?

A. Yes B. No

APPENDIX IV: LABORATORY RESULTS

Macroscopic appearance:

First sample.....

Second sample.....

Microscopic appearance:

First sample.....

Second sample.....

Other comments:

Name and signature of the laboratory personnel.....

Name and signature of the researcher.....

APPENDIX V: APPROVAL LETTER

The Republic of
Uganda

FOR ANY CORRESPONDENCE ON
THIS SUBJECT PLEASE QUOTE NO.

CHINA-UGANDA FRIENDSHIP HOSPITAL, NAGURU

P. O. Box 20145,

Nakawa, Uganda

Tel: Hospital Director: +256-41289741

General Line: +256-414289740

CHINA AID

Ref: ADM/N/11/07/24

11th July, 2024

Rubangakene Fred

Medical Laboratory Training School
JINJA

Thru: Hospital Director

*Forwarded
A. Kamuganga*

PERMISSION TO CONDUCT RESEARCH

Reference is made to your letter requesting this Hospital to grant you permission to conduct a research, The research topic is “ **Factors influencing the Prevalence of Tuberculosis among Adult patients Accessing Health Services at China-Uganda Friendship Hospital Naguru .**” This is to inform you that permission has been granted. You will work under the supervision of **Head Laboratory**

At the end of the study, you are obliged to share the research findings with the Hospital by providing a copy of the dissertation to the Research and Ethics Committee; and will be provided with a letter confirming completion of the study.

Dr. Wanyama John

CHAIRMAN RESEARCH AND ETHICS COMMITTEE

Cc: Head Laboratory

APPENDIX VI: MAP SHOWING LOCATION OF CHINA UGANDA FRIENDSHIP HOSPITAL, NAGURU IN KAMPALA

APPENDIX VII: STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES FOR GENEXPERT

Principle

The Xpert MTB/RIF test for use with the Cepheid GeneXpert® System is a semi-quantitative nested real-time. PCR *in vitro* diagnostic test for: 1) the detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTB complex) DNA in sputum samples.

1. Material

- GeneXpert Dx System equipped with Gx Dx software version 4.3 or higher, GeneXpert instrument, computer, barcode reader, and Operator Manual
- Optional Printer
- The Xpert MTB/RIF kit (GXMTB/RIF-10 or GXMTB/RIF-50) contains sufficient reagents to process 10/50 patient or quality-control specimens:
 - Sample Reagent (Sodium Hydroxide and Isopropanol, 8 mL per cartridge which is clear, ranging from colorless to golden yellow)
 - Sterile disposable transfer pipettes
- Sterile screw-capped specimen collection containers
- Disposable Gloves
- Labels and/or indelible labeling marker
- Sterile pipettes (2 mL) for sample processing

2. Storage and Handling

- Store the Xpert MTB/RIF cartridges and reagents at 2–28 °C.
- Do not use reagents or cartridges that have passed the expiration date.
- Do not open a cartridge until you are ready to perform testing.
- Use the cartridge within 4 hours after opening the cartridge lid.
- The cartridge is stable up to 7 days after opening the package (Kit of 50).

3. Procedure

i. Sputum Sediments

- Do not accept specimens with obvious food particles or other solid particulates.
- Process only as many samples at one time as there are modules available to run the test on the GeneXpert Dx System.
- Sputum sediments prepared according to the method of Kent and Kubica and re-suspended in 67mM Phosphate/H₂O buffer can be tested using XpertMTB/RIF. Once the re-suspension is prepared for standard laboratory smear or culture tests, ensure at least 0.5 mL of re-suspended sediment is available to run Xpert MTB/RIF.

- 1) Label each Xpert MTB/RIF cartridge with the sample ID. (Write on the sides of the cartridge or affix ID label.) Note: Do not put the label on the lid of the cartridge or obstruct the existing 2D barcode on the cartridge.
- 2) Transfer at least 0.5 mL of the total re-suspension pellet to a conical, screwcapped tube for the Xpert MTB/RIF using a sterile transfer pipette. Alternatively, the entire sample may be processed in the original tube.
- 3) Store re-suspended sediments at 2–8 °C if they are not immediately processed for Xpert MTB/RIF. Do not store for more than 12 hours.
- 4) Add 1.5 mL of Xpert MTB/RIF Sample Reagent (SR) to 0.5 mL of resuspended sediment sample using a sterile transfer pipette.
- 5) Shake vigorously 10 – 20 times. Note: One back-and-forth movement is a single shake.
- 6) Incubate the specimen for 15 minutes at room temperature. At one point between 5 and 10 minutes of the incubation, again shake the specimen vigorously 10 – 20 times. Samples should be liquefied with no visible clumps of sputum. Particulate matter may exist that is not part of the sample.

ii. Preparing the Cartridge

Important: Start the test within 30 minutes of adding the sample to the cartridge.

- 1) Using the sterile transfer pipette provided, aspirate the liquefied sample into the transfer pipette until the meniscus is above the minimum mark. Do not process the sample further if there is insufficient volume.
- 2) Open the cartridge lid. Transfer sample into the open port of the Xpert MTB/RIF cartridge. See picture below. Dispense slowly to minimize the risk of aerosol formation.
- 3) Close the cartridge lid. Make sure the lid snaps firmly into place. Remaining liquefied sample may be kept for up to 12 hours at 2 – 8 °C should repeating the test be required.

iii. Starting the Test

This section lists the basic steps of running the test.

- 1) Turn on the computer, and then turn on the GeneXpert Dx instrument.
- 2) On the Windows® desktop, double-click the GeneXpert Dx shortcut icon.
- 3) Log on to the GeneXpert Dx System software using your username and password.
- 4) In the GeneXpert Dx System window, click Create Test.
- 5) Scan or type in the Patient ID (optional). If typing the Patient ID, make sure the Patient ID is typed correctly. The Patient ID is associated with the test results and is shown in the View Results window.

- 6) Scan or type in the Sample ID. If typing the Sample ID, make sure the Sample ID is typed correctly. The Sample ID is associated with the test results and is shown in the View Results window and all reports.
- 7) Scan the barcode on the Xpert MTB/RIF cartridge. The Create Test window appears. Using the barcode information, the software automatically fills the boxes for the following fields: Select Assay, Reagent Lot ID, Cartridge SN, and Expiration Date.
- 8) Click Start Test. In the dialog box that appears, type your password if requested.
- 9) Open the instrument module door with the blinking green light and load the cartridge.
- 10) Close the door. The test starts and the green light stops blinking. When the test is finished, the light turns off.
- 11) Wait until the system releases the door lock at the end of the run, then open the module door and remove the cartridge.
- 12) Dispose of used cartridges in the appropriate specimen waste containers according to your institution's standard practices.